

Forage calibration transfer between near infrared laboratory and handheld instruments

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The objective of this trial was to transfer calibration from a laboratory instrument to be used by two different handheld spectrometers. One hundred twenty samples of dried ground (1mm) corn plant or corn ear were scanned with spectrometers, two handheld and one laboratory: 1) a diode array (DA) with 256 diodes, 950–1650 every 2nm (AuroraNir, GraiNit s.r.l.); 2) a digital light processing (DLP) also scanning between 950 and 1650 every 2nm (Texas Instrument, USA); 3) Foss NIRSystem 5000 (LAB) scanning between 1100 and 1498 every 2nm (Foss, DK). Each instrument had a different sample presentation and scanning mode. For the DA, samples were scanned at two spots, 5 spots for the DLP and 24 scans in a rotating ring cup for the LAB. All repeated scans were averaged by sample before any computation. Samples were analysed for crude protein (CP), neutral detergent fibre (NDF), and starch. The data set was divided in 20 samples for validation and 100 for calibration. Within the calibration set, a subset of 20 samples was selected to evaluate instrument-to-instrument differences and calculate transfer functions (standardization). All the calculations were performed using UCAL 4.0 (Unity Scientific, USA). Standardization algorithms tested were: spectral bias, Shenk and Westerhaus (1991) method, and piece-wise direct standardization (Bouveresse and Massart, 1996). Predicting the DA validation samples, the SEP for CP was 0.52 vs. 0.72, for NDF was 2.09 vs. 2.19, and for starch was 2.74 vs. 2.47, for DA and LAB transferred, respectively. The LAB calibration transferred to DLP had very large biases of prediction for NDF (3.83 %DM) and starch (-4.25 %DM), but a small bias for CP (-0.136 %DM). Compared to the prediction performances with the original handheld, the error of the LAB-transferred prediction was similar for the DA but much higher for the DLP.

Keywords: calibration transfer

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